

Development of a low-cost thermographic instrument for water detection

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Highlights

- We developed a low-cost thermographic instrument for water detection based on FLIR technology.
- The camera can be triggered under a range of flow conditions.
- Waters of different temperature (0.05°C) can be differentiated with the instrument.

Introduction

Infrared thermography has been used in a range of water-related applications. Hare *et al.* (2015) used the technology to detect groundwater inputs along a natural waterway. The technology has been used to detect leakage from water supply pipes (Bach & Kodikara, 2017), along with infiltration in sewer pipes (Lepot *et al.*, 2017). An important strength of the technology is the ability to capture dynamics of the system of interest. For example, thermal sensors can be triggered in response to rain events and the evolution of the thermograph can be readily captured. With the rapid development of low-cost computing (e.g. Arduino, Raspberry Pi), there is significant potential to develop low-cost thermographic instruments for water detection. Such instruments offer numerous benefits over ‘off the shelf’ instruments (Table 1). In this work, we describe the development of a low-cost thermographic instrument in order to observe groundwater interaction in receiving waters. The assumption is that the infrared camera will be able to detect, quantify (if possible) and record (visualise) temperature differences between groundwater and surface water.

Table 1: Typical features of thermographic instruments.

	‘Off the shelf’ sensors	Low-cost sensors
Easy to buy	√	√
Higher resolution imagery	√	X
Ready to use	√	X
User friendly	√	X
Relatively lower cost	X	√
High compatibility with other equipment/sensors	X	√
Reputable sensor manufacturer (FLIR)	√	√
Open source	X	√
Can process data onboard	X	√
Compatible with any type of external trigger	X	√
Compatible with real-time monitoring	X	√

Methodology

We based our instrument on FLIR technology—the Lepton 3.5, the same thermographic sensor found in many “off the shelf” products (FLIR Systems, 2018). The camera has a resolution of 160 x 120 pixels and a thermal sensitivity of 50 mK (0.050° C). The spectral range is longwave infrared 8-14 μm and the camera consumes nominally less than 200mW. The size of the system is 10.50 x 12.70 x 7.14 [mm] for a weight under 1 gram. The camera needs to be mounted on a bracket board. This particular sensor can be purchased as a developer version. We sought to determine how the sensor could be used as part of a low-cost instrument.

Computer hardware and power management

We found that the thermographic sensor could be readily connected to a Raspberry Pi (version 3 model B+ in our case), through the GPIO. The camera connector bus can be left empty to connect a ‘normal’ (not IR) camera if needed. This meant that thermographic images could be matched with visual ones.

As the instrument is to be deployed in the field, we required a power management system which relied solely on batteries. The power consumption of the Raspberry Pi is relatively high (5 V/2.5 A ; <https://static.raspberrypi.org/files/product-briefs/Raspberry-Pi-Model-Bplus-Product-Brief.pdf>) compared to other low-cost boards such as Arduino or Pycom. It was deemed not practical to have the Raspberry Pi powered continuously. Instead, we coupled it with a Witty Pi along with a level switch and recycling timer. The Witty Pi provides a real-time clock for the Raspberry Pi in order to update the Pi’s internal clock. The Witty Pi can also be used to power on the Raspberry Pi, but in our application the wakeup of the computer is trigger based on the water level (level switch). Various start-up scripts are executed (see below) and the computer is shut down by itself. The recycling timer power cycled the Raspberry Pi every 15-mins until flow receded.

Control logic

Basic bash and python scripting ensured that once powered, the instrument captured a 160x120 pixel thermographic image along with an eight-megapixel visual one. The files were stored to an SD card with a timestamp provided by the Witty Pi. In another prototype, the files were sent directly to a server via the 4G mobile telecommunication network. Such scripting highlights the flexibility of the instrument over ‘off the shelf’ products, particularly in regards to how frequently data is collected and where it is stored. The figure 1 below presents the sequence of operation of the system.

Figure 1: Basic components of the low-cost thermographic instrument and sequence of operation

Results and Discussion

We deployed the instrument in the field for several weeks—within the streambed of a headwater stream—but unfortunately there were no rain events large enough to generate flow and thus trigger the device. That said, Figure 2 below illustrates output from the instrument. Figure 2 highlights the importance of combining a thermographic image with a visual one. The grey and colour scales are optimized for each thermal picture pixel matrix, based on the minimum and maximum temperatures observed. It is planned to install soil temperature sensors in the field to verify the thermal readings and better calibrate the grey and colour scales. Appropriate thermal scaling of the images onboard the camera can also help to filter out unwanted extremes.

Figure 2: Example of output from the visual camera (upper left) and infrared camera: matrix of temperature (upper right), artificially colored thermal image (bottom left) and greyscale thermal image (bottom right).

The upper right show a part of the 160x120 pixels matrix for clarity (values are expressed Kelvin degrees times 100).

Further testing of the instrument will include:

- Confirm that the sensitivity of the camera is compatible with the detection of sub-surface groundwater intrusion with on-going seasonal point monitoring of temperature using standalone dataloggers.
- Selection of the infrared transmissive window required to waterproof the system.
- Finding the optimal distance between the IR camera and the stream: trade-off between image resolution and field of view.
- Further optimization of power management.
- Viewing of live data.
- Potential for remote triggering.

References

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